

THE TERMINOLOGICAL DIVERSITY OF AMERICAN ENGLISH VARIETIES

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Annotation: This article analyzes by leading experts on the types of English languages discussed that are designed to provide students with detailed information about the languages they speak or hear around them, based on comprehensive coverage of their underlying language systems. The socio-cultural context of the resulting languages and dialects is introduced. Each is divided into specific US dialects and varieties of American English, with problem sets and recommended further reading to reinforce key concepts and new linguistic terminology in each, and to encourage further study of the languages.

Key terms: American English, British English, language varieties, concepts, sociolinguistics, socio-cultural context, dialect.

Background knowledge

Manifestations of the linguistic features of the American English language The English language brought to North America in the 17th - 18th centuries. And modified under the influence of various external and internal factors, it became widespread and became the most commonly used and studied language. Not enshrined in the US Constitution, it is in fact the official language and native language of 80% of the world's people and 70% of those living in America. In addition, from the middle of the twentieth century, the American version of the English language began to penetrate the speech of foreign-speaking peoples. Some people don't like this kind of dominance. Although, this often happens

voluntarily, for example, along with the use of new terms when using textbooks on management, marketing, when reading articles in American English, when visiting American websites, etc. Language changes improve and enrich any language. The history of each language is built on unique linguistic material. At the same time, changes in the language system are determined by the development of society and its culture. An integral part of a society's culture is speech style. Literary style is the most studied because it is more static. Apparently because the literary norm adopted in the USA is a modified version of the British norm. It follows that when studying American English, one should still explore the conversational style more deeply. The main difficulty in studying it is that, unlike literary, it is very mobile. At the same time, the colloquial style does not violate the generally accepted norms of literary speech, despite the inherent freedom in the choice of means. The fact is that the dynamics of the conversational style are influenced by the real subject situation around the speech itself. Therefore, there is a tendency to extremely shorten the statement, to remove individual components altogether. And yet this does not interfere with the correct perception of colloquial phrases. For Americans, such guidelines are, first of all, material, hedonistic, moral and aesthetic values, on the basis of which their ideological values are based.”¹. In colloquial speech there is a great process of borrowing and transformation of English words. An example would be such transformed words as: bucks dollars (from the American buck dollar), to use (from the English use to use), cool excellent, wonderful (from the word cool cool). This is how Americans form their own moral standards that are inherent to them, while testing social norms for effectiveness”.

Methodology

¹ 18. Леонтович , О.А. Россия и США : введение в межкультурную коммуникацию / О.А. Леонтович . Волгоград : Перемена , 2012. - 400 с .

By introducing learners to the linguistic, social, cultural, and political underpinnings of these distinct dialects and the changes in English, languages, and dialects in the United States, this is an ideal text for those interested in linguistic diversity in the United States, in courses in sociolinguistics, language and culture, and the study of language that provides information such as change. Today two opposing trends are emerging in the American communication system. On the one hand, status plays an important role in the system of American values. On the other hand, democratic traditions require that communication remain informal and symmetrical. Social inequality in the process of communication is smoothed out and manifests itself not so much in an explicit, but in an implicit form

Data collection and Analysis

When we talk about terminological diversity, we mainly mean vocabulary and its forms. As we noted above in the context of English language use, English is now widely used as a world language, and its diversity can be somewhat daunting for learners. That is, regionally, American English is very different from British English. There is a stereotype that the British speak more correctly than Americans. However, contrary to popular belief, there is no correct version of the language. Each dialect reflects the cultural characteristics of the people of different countries.

British and American English, like any dialect, have some differences in grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation. Which option to follow, depends on the learners and the users of the language. Referring to the terminological diversity based on the type of English, this diversity is analyzed by comparing American English with British English. Below, the terms in American English are compared with the existing terms in British English, dividing the dictionaries into categories. (see table)

Terminological diversity of English varieties			
№	Sphere	British English	American English

I.	People and society	an apartment / a flat	an apartment
		crazy / mad	Crazy
		a nappy	a diaper
		a line / a queue	a line
		Angry	Mad
		Nasty	Mean
		Stingy / mean	Stingy
		a toilet / a lavatory	a restroom
II.	Work And business	a receptionist	a desk clerk
		Labour	Labor
		a pay rise	a raise
		a fortnight	two weeks
III.	Law and order	a lawyer/ a barrister	a lawyer
		a solicitor	an attorney
		Prison	Jail
		a licence	a license
IV.	Health	an offence	an offense
		a (doctor's) surgery	a doctor's office
V.	Money and shopping	a chemist	a drugstore a pharmacy
		a cheque	a check
		a bill	A bill / a check
		an estate agent	a realtor
		a shop assistant	a sales clerk
VI.		a shop	a store
		a hob	a burner
		a tin	a can

	Food and drinks	a sweet	a candy
		Crisps	(potato) chips
		a biscuit	a cookie
		Cutlery	Silverware
		a cooker	a stove
		a takeaway	a takeout
VII.	Education and Study	a primary school	an elementary school a junior school
		a secondary school	a high school / a senior school
		a rubber	an eraser
		a mark	a grade
		a head / a headteacher a headmaster / a headmistress	a principal
		a test	a quiz
		a break	a recess
VIII.	Science and technology	an aerial	an antenna
		a mobile phone	a cell phone
		a lift	an elevator
		a torch	a flashlight
IX.	Weather and environment	city centre	Downtown
		Autumn	Fall
		a dustbin	a garbage can
		a rubbish / a litter bin	a trash can
		Rubbish	Garbage / trash
		a garden	a yard
a neighbour	a neighbor		

		a neighbourhood	a neighborhood
X.	Travel and transport	an aeroplane	an airplane
		Petrol	Gas / gasoline
		the main road	a highway
		a motorway	a freeway
		a single (ticket)	a one-way (ticket)
		a car park	a parking lot
		a pavement	a sidewalk
		a railway	a railroad
		the underground	a subway
		a tyre	a tire
		a caravan	a trailer
		a truck / a van / a lorry	a truck
		a holiday	a vacation
a windscreen	a windshield		
XI.	Hobby and sport	American football	Football
		Soccer / football	Soccer
		Trainers	Sneakers
		Athletics	track and field
		to do practise	to take practice
XII.	Entertainment and relaxation	Humour	Humor
		a film	a movie
		a cinema	a movie theater
		a theatre	a theater
		a talk show / a chat show	a talk show
		a TV programme	a TV program
XIII.		a wardrobe / a cupboard	a closet

Fashion and design	Colour	Color
	turn-ups	Cuffs
	Modelling	Modeling
	Trousers	Pants / slacks
	a sweater / a jumper / a jersey	a sweater
	a waistcoat	a vest
	a zip	a zipper

Table 1 - Terminological diversity of English varieties

If we pay attention to the part of practical analysis, among the learners of English as a foreign language, the terminological variety of American English and the terminological variety of British English are used more often. In order to analyze this, the dictionaries used in the speech of the students of the "Uzbekistan State University of World Languages" and in the speech of students in many language courses in Tashkent were analyzed. According to the results of the analysis:

Figure 1 Use of English dialects

The result shows that English as a foreign language learners in language courses tend to try to use a little more American dialect in their speech. Among the university students, words related to the British dialect appeared more in their speech. The participants of both groups showed the same mixture, that is, words related to the American English and British English dialects and a slightly mixed pronunciation.

Result and Discussion

It is difficult to imagine spoken English, as well as the language of the media and even literary works, without two frequently repeated short words to do and to get. Those who speak English can no longer do without these ubiquitous and almost utilitarian verbs, which are often used to facilitate the syntactic construction of a sentence or to avoid repetition. However, most often this phrase carries a different lexical load, or gives the expression an emotional connotation (she's got the cold - she has a cold; don't get your wet - don't get your feet wet). We see that the phrase to get gives color to speech and determines the style of narration; it is often used to concisely and most accurately describe any concepts or states that cannot be defined using normative vocabulary, but only using colloquial vocabulary.

A further study analyzed the extent to which recognized language learners could use and understand the terminology of words related to the American English dialect. Language learners were given a test on the above American English and British English terminology, and several language learners were selected as research subjects and tested. This test tested the ability to understand the vocabulary of the American English dialect. Each of them was given a test based on 30 selected vocabulary words, and the result is shown in the diagram below.

Figure 2. Analysis of knowledge and understanding of American English terminology

Through the following formula the overall score is identified:

$$23+24+20+24+25+21+20+23+24+21+25+23+21+26+21=$$

$$22.7 \qquad 22.7*100/30=75.6$$

The total number of participants and its equal distribution was 22.7. Its percentage was 75.6%.

Figure 3.3 Percentage of knowledge of American English terminology

Above, we got acquainted with the analysis of indicators of the use of American English terminology. In general, American English terminology is used more often in which aspect or skill. For this reason, it was analyzed in which aspects the terminology of words related to the American dialect is used more among the learners of English as a foreign language. (see figure)

Figure 3. Aspects of using American English terminology.

American English dialect terms have been confirmed to be the most frequently encountered aspect by language learners. Because language learners are passionate about American music and movies, they often encounter American dialects through listening and viewing. The next indicator is the speaking aspect, because language learners try to perform what they have learned through listening through speaking, which is a productive skill. Language learners often encounter American English terminology in their reading materials while reading news about American dialects online. And the least used area is writing, mainly in the process of forming writing skills, based on British English standards, British English terminology was used more. This, in turn, is a clear reason why American English terminology is rarely found in writing skills.

Conclusion

Language changes improve and enrich any language. The history of each language British and American English is built on unique linguistic material. At the same time, changes in the language system are determined by the development of society and its culture. An integral part of a society's culture is speech style. Literary style is the most studied because it is more static. Apparently because the literary norm adopted in the USA is a modified version of the British norm. It follows that when studying American English, one should still explore the conversational style more deeply. The main difficulty in studying it is that, unlike literary, it is very mobile. At the same time, the colloquial style does not violate the generally accepted norms of literary speech, despite the inherent freedom in the choice of means. The fact is that the dynamics of the conversational style are influenced by the real subject situation around the speech itself.

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